

Study on doping of specialty silica optical fibers for Tm-fiber lasers and amplifiers with antimony oxide

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ABSTRACT

Rare-earth doped optical fibers are widely used as a heart of fiber lasers and amplifiers. In this paper we deal with study of the MCVD process of fabrication of preforms with low-phonon Sb_2O_3 and influence of achieved core composition on optical properties of thulium-doped optical fibers used for optical generation at 1900-2000 nm spectral region. The solution-doping method and nanoparticle-doping method extending the MCVD method were used for the fabrication of preforms. A maximum of 0.15 mol% Sb_2O_3 in the core of preforms was achieved. It corresponds to usual role of Sb_2O_3 as refining agent in glass fabrication. The same spatial distribution of Sb_2O_3 together with Tm^{3+} ions and Al_2O_3 in the core was observed, so welcome localization of all dopants in nanometer-atomic scale can be expected. Tm^{3+} doped fibers exhibited good lasing characteristics at 1950 nm, fiber doped with Sb_2O_3 exhibited slightly higher SLE in comparison to fiber undoped with Sb_2O_3 . The difference is not substantial but proportional to achieved level of doping.

Keywords: Optical fiber, fiber laser, fiber amplifier, antimony oxide, aluminum oxide, thulium, MCVD

INTRODUCTION

Rare-earth (RE) doped optical fibers are widely used as a heart of fiber lasers and amplifiers for years [1]. Erbium-doped fiber amplifiers operating at around 1550 nm (telecom C-band) can serve as a typical example widely used in today's telecoms. Fiber amplifiers or fiber lasers operating outside C-band, e.g. at S-band around 1470 nm or at 1900-2000 nm spectral range, based on silica fibers compatible with telecom network, are welcome contribution to this field.

Amplification at S-band was theoretically studied by Peterka [2]; amplification up to 20 dB at 1470 nm was predicted on condition of optimized fiber parameters like numerical aperture, core diameter and proper core material composition. Study of efficiency and thermal behavior of Tm^{3+} -doped fiber lasers operating at around 1800-1900 nm have been reported [3-4]. Potential enhancement of fluorescence of RE ions by local doping of their vicinity in glass matrix with low-phonon materials was studied E.g. by [5-7].

Doping of preforms for optical fiber drawing with Sb_2O_3 was successfully demonstrated by Vapor Axial Deposition [8]. This method is of chemical vapor deposition (CVD) concept but completely different from the Modified Chemical Vapor Deposition (MCVD) method [9] in which evaporation of volatile components (like Sb_2O_3) represents quite severe problem. The process of fabrication of Sb_2O_3 -doped preforms by the MCVD was studied E.g. by Dianov's group [10].

In this paper we deal with study of the MCVD process of fabrication of preforms with Sb_2O_3 and influence of achieved core composition on optical properties of Tm^{3+} -doped optical fibers used for optical generation at 1900-2000 nm spectral region. Influence of modification of glass matrix composition and of some preform fabrication steps were investigated.

EXPERIMENT

Initial set of preforms with cores of composition Tm^{3+} - Al_2O_3 - Sb_2O_3 - SiO_2 was prepared by the MCVD method extended by solution-doping [11] from TmCl_3 , AlCl_3 and SbCl_3 solid-state starting materials. Doped frits were sintered

under oxygen atmosphere; attention was given to thermal treatment regime (processing temperatures 1850-2100 °C, exposition 22-52 min) with the aim to decrease evaporation of volatile Sb_2O_3 from the core layer. The core of sample 0914 was prepared from two doped layers by repeated solution-doping process. Preforms and segments uncollapsed tubes were characterized by concentration profile by electron microprobe analysis - EMA (JEOL JXA-8230) and by refractive-index profile - RIP (A2600, Photon Kinetics). Based on results achieved two preforms with and without Sb_2O_3 in the core were fabricated by nanoparticle-doping method [12] from TmCl_3 and Al_2O_3 nanoparticles. Preform assigned for Sb_2O_3 doping was sintered under SbCl_5 (liquid state) atmosphere. Two fibers with and without Sb_2O_3 in the core were drawn with cutoff optimized at around 1540 nm and of conventional diameter 125 μm . They were characterized by attenuation measurements and by lasing characteristics in Fabry-Perot arrangement with EDFL source [13].

RESULTS

Preforms with concentration of Tm^{3+} of several thousand ppm and low content of Sb_2O_3 were prepared (Tab. 1). Since Sb_2O_3 belongs to glassforming oxides, no crystallization effects or phase separation were observed.

Tab 1. Chemical composition of fabricated preforms determined by EMA

sample	Sb_2O_3 [wt%]	Sb_2O_3 [mol%]	Al_2O_3 [mol%]	GeO_2 [mol%]	Tm^{3+} [ppm]
0903-tube	2.4	0.6	7	9	5000
0903 prf	0.7	0.2	7.5	0.4	4000
0911-tube	0.1	0.05	7	14	5000
0911-prf	3.0	0.9	9	0.4	2000
0914-tube	10.4	2.7	7	5	5000
0914-prf	0.8	0.2	12	0.4	2000
1618-prf	0	0	8.7	0	5000
1816-prf	0.6	0.15	7.8	0	5000

A significant difference between concentration of Sb_2O_3 in collapsed preform and in doped substrate tube was observed. This difference can be explained just by evaporation of volatile Sb_2O_3 during collapse of the tube to preform. No substantial influence of variations of tube collapsing on final content of Sb_2O_3 in preforms was observed. The obtained Sb_2O_3 concentrations in tubes as well as in preform cores were uniquely determined (several times higher than limit of detection of the analytical method). Higher Sb_2O_3 content (2.7 mol%) was found at uncollapsed tube which core was prepared from two layers and so the core layer thickness was larger in comparison to other samples.

Fig. 1 EMA concentration profile of preforms with and without Sb_2O_3 selected for fiber

Fig. 2 RIPs of preforms with and without Sb_2O_3 for drawing of optical fibers

EMA concentration profiles of preforms with and without Sb_2O_3 drawn to optical fibers can be seen in Fig. 1. No central dip of Al_2O_3 around axis of preform can be observed thanks to non-volatility of Al_2O_3 in comparison to silica matrix. Profiles of Al_2O_3 , of Tm^{3+} and of Sb_2O_3 exhibit the same features (without central dip) and so desired local localization of Sb_2O_3 to Al_2O_3 and Tm^{3+} together can be concluded.

RIPs of preforms are depicted in Fig. 2; no central dip of refractive index can be observed. It can be attributed to high content of Al_2O_3 and low content of evaporating Sb_2O_3 . RIPs correspond to the content of dopants (Fig. 1).

Absorption losses of Tm^{3+} (Fig. 3) were determined at spectral region 1400-2000 nm using ~40 mm segments of fibers. The background losses (Tab. 1) were observed in spectral range 870-960 nm and determined by the cut-back method.

Fig. 3 Absorption losses and background losses of fiber without and with Sb_2O_3 in the core

Fig. 4 Lasing characteristics of fiber with and without Sb_2O_3

Concentrations of Tm^{3+} ions in particular segments of fibers were calculated [13] and summarized in Tab. 2. These values are in good agreement with concentrations determined by EMA. Achieved background losses are quite low, comparable each other, and proving reasonable quality of elaborated process of fabrication of doped fibers. Lasing characteristics (Fig. 4) are summarized in Tab. 2.

Tab. 2 Properties of drawn fibers with and without Sb_2O_3

sample	α 1650 nm [dB/m]	C Tm^{3+} [ppm]	Background losses [dB/km]	$\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{Tm}^{3+}$	threshold [W]	SLE_1950 nm [%]
1618	249	5900	34	18	~ 0	67
1816	224	5300	34	16	~ 0	68.2

Both samples implemented into fiber laser setup exhibited low threshold of lasing and high SLE observed at 1950 nm. These values are comparable with thulium fiber lasers of good quality. Higher SLE was observed with fiber containing Sb_2O_3 in the core. The difference is not a big one and it is adequate to small amount of Sb_2O_3 deposited into fiber core. The data supporting the results of this study are available in [14].

CONCLUSIONS

Keeping of higher content of constituents of lower melting point in glass during sintering or melting processes is generally hard, namely in case of high-silica glass fabrication performed at around 2000 °C. So, the problem of volatility of dopants like P_2O_5 , Sb_2O_3 , PbO or GeO_2 is inherent to fabrication of silica optical fibers. Several tricks such as modification of glass matrix composition with dopants of higher melting point (alumina), modification of preform collapsing process, modification of thickness of core layer were tested.

Although the above-mentioned approaches were successfully employed for MCVD fabrication of silica-based preforms and fibers highly doped with P_2O_5 , in this study maximally 0.15 mol% Sb_2O_3 in the core of preforms was achieved. It corresponds to usual role of Sb_2O_3 as refining agent in glass fabrication. The same spatial distribution of Sb_2O_3 together with Tm^{3+} ions and Al_2O_3 in the core was observed, so welcome localization of all dopants in nanometer-atomic scale can be expected. This experience can be generalized for preparation of silica preforms doped with other volatile components like Bi_2O_3 .

Tm^{3+} doped fibers exhibited good lasing characteristics at 1950 nm, fiber doped with Sb_2O_3 exhibited slightly higher SLE in comparison to fiber undoped with Sb_2O_3 . The difference is not substantial but proportional to achieved level of doping.

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